

FELLOWSHIP

MAY 2026

Guwahati

City Vision Document

A citizen-led vision narrative capturing stories,
concerns, and hopes for the city's future

About the Vision Document

This City Vision Document is a reflective learning assignment carried out as part of the Nāgrika Fellowship Programme. It is based on a limited number of conversations with citizens and observational research conducted over a few months by the fellow. The document does not claim to represent the complete or official vision of the city, but rather offers a citizen-led snapshot—built through individual stories, insights, and lived experiences gathered during the fellowship. The perspectives shared here reflect the voices of a few residents, selected to capture a range of age groups, professions, and neighborhoods. The document is not exhaustive and may not include all communities or viewpoints. This document is intended as a starting point for dialogue and reflection. We hope it encourages broader conversations about the city’s identity, challenges, and future possibilities.

The research and writing were undertaken independently by the fellow, within a framework of structured guidance provided by Nāgrika. This included thematic prompts, narrative-building exercises, regular mentorship and feedback sessions, all designed to support the fellow in shaping their city’s vision. The interpretations and final content remain those of the fellow.

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Nāgrika Fellowship

The **Nāgrika Fellowship Programme** has been designed to empower young individuals from diverse educational and geographic backgrounds, including students, gap-year participants, and early-career researchers, to positively engage with the history, socio-economic, governance, and cultural context of their cities. Focused on the youth of small and mid-sized cities, the fellowship is building local knowledge, enabling civic consciousness, and developing thought leaders who can address environmental, social, and infrastructural challenges. Over a period of six months, fellows gained tools for understanding and engaging with their cities.

A key component of the fellowship is the development of the **City Vision Document** by the fellows. This document is an emotionally grounded reflection of how citizens experience and imagine their city. Developed through conversations with diverse residents of the fellows' cities, it weaves together stories of everyday life, places of belonging, pressing concerns, and aspirations for the future. The document captures lived experiences and heartfelt insights to build a narrative that is authentic, accessible, and community-driven. It serves not only as a record of local voices but also as an invitation to reimagine the city through the eyes of those who call it home.

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Everyday Life

This theme explores the daily rhythms, routines, and interactions that shape how people experience their city. It highlights the ordinary yet meaningful details of our city's life and how citizens connect with their surroundings on a regular basis.

Places of Belonging

Places of Belonging are spaces that hold emotional, cultural, or social significance for residents. This theme focuses on spaces that provide identity, memory, and a sense of home, the places where we feel connected, seen, and grounded.

Voices of Concern

This theme brings out the issues and challenges that citizens face in their day-to-day lives such as poor infrastructure, lack of public transport, disappearing green spaces, water or waste management issues, safety concerns, or loss of cultural heritage.

Dreams for Tomorrow

Dreams for Tomorrow reflects citizens' aspirations for the city's future. This theme brings forward ideas, hopes, and solutions imagined by the people who live in and care for the city.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This City Vision Document is above all a collective story. The Nāgrika fellowship made it possible. They gave me the time, the trust, and the platform to step back from my daily routines and really listen to the city I've called home for twenty-two years.

I'm genuinely grateful to the entire Nāgrika team. They believed that the voices of ordinary *Guwahatians* deserve to shape their city's own narrative. Their guidance document and template helped sharpen this draft, yet the heart of it still comes from the streets, the ghats, the cafés, and the living rooms of Guwahati.

My deepest thanks go to every person I interviewed. A big 'Thank You' to Mrinmoyee Sarmah Bordoloi, Swapnil Dutta, Avilasha Bhowmik, Disha Dutta, Mohixit Goswami, Dudulmoni Sarmah, Mallika Sarmah, Kangkan Bordoloi, Hrishikesh Medhi, Mayur Gopendra Das, Arhana Bhuyan, Shahina Jannat, Rahul Rohan Paul, Sabique Hasan Ahmed, Bhargab Bezbaruah, Dr. Rashmi Sarmah, Jeet Pathak, Dr. Sayanika Dutta, Abhijnan Barhoi, Pranabjit Bordoloi, Arunava Borah, Syeda Tarrannum Shahzadi, Himparna Das, Arghya Saha and Adri Sarkar. You handed me the living pulse of the city. Your stories of laughter, your frustrations, your memories of quieter mornings at Dighalipukhuri, your passionate love for the *Xihu*, and your quiet dreams for a cleaner, kinder Guwahati have become the backbone of this document. I hope this city vision document that I have drafted has done justice to your words.

I'm also grateful to my family and friends. They put up with my endless note-taking during family outings, my distracted evenings, and those sudden detours to random places in Guwahati just to feel the place again. Their patience and gentle reminders that this work mattered kept me going, and I was also grateful for the little snacks they kept treating me to keep me motivated.

Finally, I'm offering this document back to the people of Guwahati with humility and hope. This is not a finished plan. It's an invitation to keep the conversation alive, to hold our leaders accountable, and to remind one another that the soul of this city has always lived in its people. May the stories that we have shared here become the glimmer of hope that helps us build a future for the 'Gateway to the Northeast' worthy of the river that has carried us for centuries.

Thank you, Guwahati.

-Ankita Sarmah Bordoloi

Why this Vision Document?

When the question arises that who gets to write the story of the city Guwahati, the answer for a long period of time has been outsiders, basically planners sitting in distant offices, experts who fly in for a few days, consultants with data but little sense of what it feels like to have the ‘Tekeli Pitha’ from roadside shops with a cup of ‘Lal Saah’ (Black Tea) during a morning walk by the river Brahmaputra. This document is intended to change that very idea.

There's a need for a document that reflects the lived realities of the citizens of Guwahati in a manner that can connect everyone to the very core of the city. The people who actually live in Guwahati are the ones best qualified to tell its story. They have walked its streets through quiet mornings and chaotic evenings. They have seen the city shift from a sleepy river town to a bustling gateway with more and more tourists every other day. They understand its contradictions, the deep sense of belonging that survives traffic jams and construction dust, the warmth that lingers in tea-stall addas and in the theatre performances of Rabindra Bhawan. They carry the lived experience, the quiet frustrations, the small joys, and the grounded dreams that no objective survey or satellite image can ever capture.

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Every place holds itself together through some invisible thread. In Guwahati it is the easy community that forms without invitation, the natural flow of conversations at local parks, the shared pride of the city when it declared the Xihu (Gangetic River Dolphin) as the official city animal in 2016, the way people are voicing together in order to protect Deepor Beel, which is a Ramsar site and freshwater lake in Guwahati, from ecological danger due rapid urban encroachment, massive garbage dumping at Boragaon, and pollution from industrial waste. That sense of trust and belonging was already here long before this document. What this document intends is to simply give it voice and serve as a reminder that the heart of the city has always come from its own people.

Meet Guwahati

“মহাবাহু ব্ৰহ্মপুত্ৰ মহামিলনৰ তীৰ্থ
কত যুগ ধৰি আহিছে প্ৰকাশি সমন্বয়ৰ অৰ্থ।”

This line by the Bard of Assam, Dr Bhupen Hazarika, roughly translates to, “O mighty Brahmaputra, pilgrimage of the great confluence; for ages you’ve revealed the meaning of harmony.”

The line always lands differently when you’re standing on the Brahmaputra riverbank in Guwahati. The city doesn’t just sit beside the river, but it grew up talking to it, arguing with it sometimes, borrowing its moods.

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In the soft haze of first light, head down to Uzan Bazar ghat, and you'll see the wide, muddy sweep rolling past, carrying silt from somewhere far upstream. If you're lucky, a Gangetic river dolphin, which is locally called 'Xihu' in Assamese, breaks the surface with that quiet, rolling arc, a flash of grey against the blue. This stretch remains one of the last real strongholds for these endangered mammals in the whole Brahmaputra system.

Long before it was called Guwahati, this place was known as 'Pragjyotishpura', the ancient 'City of Eastern Light' that was also mentioned in the Mahabharata and once the capital of the powerful Kamarupa kingdom. For centuries, it thrived as a trading centre along the Brahmaputra. The name Guwahati itself comes from 'Guwa', for areca nut, locally known as 'Tamul' in Assamese, and 'Hati', for market, which is a simple reminder that this has always been a place of everyday commerce.

Guwahati actually calls itself the 'Gateway to the Northeast', but that title feels almost secondary once you live here. What actually sets the daily rhythm is this intimate, sometimes restless relationship with the river. Students cut across lakes that eventually feed into it on their way to class. Families gather on the banks at dusk, sharing packets of muri and gossip while the water turns gold then dark.

The character of the city is shaped by its geography, riverine plains bordered by hills and by the way economic growth, education and cultural life all flow around the Brahmaputra.

For generations, the river has served as the region's main inland waterway, far more vital for navigation than for irrigation. Ports like Pandu in Guwahati have long handled

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cargo such as tea, timber, crude oil, food grains, and fertilisers, linking Assam to Kolkata and, more recently, to Bangladesh under the India-Bangladesh Protocol Route. National Waterway 2 turns the Brahmaputra into a living economic corridor, with renewed efforts to move bulk goods and revive river trade that once connected the Northeast to the rest of the country and beyond. Socio-culturally, it remains warm and community-oriented, conversations spill out of tea stalls, addas form naturally, and the presence of the rich flora and fauna gives the city a shared sense of pride and responsibility.

I've lived here twenty-two years, watched the streets go from sleepy to crowded without ever losing that deeply familiar feel. I still hunt for my next read in Panbazar's bookshops, where the shopkeepers know my taste by now—they'll slide something across the counter with a quiet “এইখন পঢ়িব পাৰা, মাইনা” (You should definitely read this, daughter) before I even ask. This familiarity and connection among the people in the city is something that can only be found in small cities. The weekends are incomplete for the locals without biting into a hot, crispy 'Singra' at Lakhi Cabin, washed down with that strong, sweet tea.

Before anything big, exams, new jobs, family decisions, people here still head up Nilachal Hill to Maa Kamakhya Temple. The hill is a steep one, but with the roads properly built, the commute to the temple is not very difficult. The energy swirling around the yoni shrine, that quiet sense of protection it provides, are important aspects that give Guwahati its own unmistakable flavour. Guwahati has something for everyone, pockets of calm amid the change that remind me why it still feels like home.

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Over the past months, I spoke with a wide cross-section of residents, young students from Cotton University, working mothers, teachers, long-time local residents, and young professionals. Conversations took place in cafés, on campus steps, during evening walks by the river, and in homes. A third-year English Literature student described her daily walk with real affection, “The walk around Dighalipukhuri is something I genuinely enjoy. The water, the trees, and the quiet movement of people, mostly students starting their day, create a calm atmosphere.” A young artist with quiet urgency about the river’s dolphins, “I think that we should be protective of our Xihu’s. They should be protected. I’ve heard that the river dolphins are really endangered and the cause of it is something that needs to be addressed.” Everyday stories of morning walks beside Dighalipukhuri, long commutes made harder by construction, quiet moments watching dolphins from the ghat, and evenings spent at adda spots revealed deeper patterns and emphasised that the city still offers pockets of calm and belonging, yet rapid expansion is putting increasing pressure on daily life and the very spaces people hold dear.

This document is built around four themes that emerged from these conversations. Everyday life captures the ordinary rhythms and quiet frictions that shape belonging. Places of Belonging explores the spaces that emotionally anchor residents. Voices of Concern surfaces the anxieties people rarely voice aloud. Dreams for Tomorrow reflects the hopes they still carry for a city that grows without losing its soul. Together, these voices show a Guwahati that is changing fast, yet remains deeply attached to its river, its dolphins, and the warmth that continues to define it.

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Guwahati: Facts in Brief

State	Assam
District	Kamrup Metropolitan
Population	Approx. 1.44 million (city, 2026 estimate)
Area	216 km ² (metropolis); metropolitan area ~1.45 million
Type of City Government	Guwahati Municipal Corporation (GMC)
Languages prevalent	Assamese (official), English, Hindi, Bengali

Meet the Citizens of Guwahati

After a series of interviews with the citizens of Guwahati, belonging to different professions, age-groups, religions, areas, etc. of the city, there was a realisation that most of the concerns of the varied group of citizens are the same. Also, the various places of belonging the citizens mentioned are found to be similar, indicating that there's a sense of commonality connecting the citizens of Guwahati despite their contrasting lives and interests.

A young man in his early twenties who has lived here for most of his life wakes up around eight in the Dispur area. There are three bus routes near his home, so he catches one of the green city buses to Cotton University, preferring the emptier ones. “I exclusively get on green buses,” he says, “and if they’re empty, even better.” The rest of the day, he keeps himself busy between lectures, time with friends on campus, and occasional wandering into Panbazar, the area he still considers the true heart of Guwahati.

A longtime housewife begins her mornings the same way she has for decades, with a careful walk along whatever footpath survives. She no longer visits Silpukhuri Park the way she used to. “Visiting Silpukhuri Park was an important part of the morning routine, but due to flyover construction, the roads are all in a terrible condition, and hence it has stopped,” she explains. She uses public transport but refuses to travel when it’s very crowded. Evenings often pull her thoughts back to Uzan Bazar. “Uzan bazar, the view of the Brahmaputra,” she says, “if that disappears, nothing matters anymore.”

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When a resident says its disappearance would leave nothing that matters, she is speaking for far more than personal nostalgia. Rapid urban expansion has already narrowed riverfront access in several areas, like Fancy Bazar, Panbazar, and Uzanbazar, with construction and new developments eating into the open views that once defined daily life here.

A young student uses sarcasm to hide his pain when he was asked about the most serious concerns in Guwahati, according to him. He remarked, “ I have 2 answers... first, those enormously wide drains, which are just filled with sewage... Also, another cause of concern is the flyovers. I think Guwahati is racing to be the city of flyovers... I fear the day that huts will be constructed on top of flyovers”.

Different people are expressing it in a different manner, but in the end, their concerns remain the same. The citizens of Guwahati are now debating between two aspects: development and preservation.

Holidays often draw people to the Kamakhya Temple. One longtime resident used to visit it quite frequently. “The Kamakhya Temple is one of the most sacred and important temples for people in Guwahati,” he says. “People feel deeply connected to the temple because it is believed that prayers offered there are fulfilled through the blessings of Maa Kamakhya. It is a very ancient temple with a long history.” People in Guwahati feel a deep sense of connection with the temple, and they have a belief that Maa Kamakhya will always be protecting the city as a guardian.

Glossary and Local Terms

Word or Phrase	Translation in English
মহাবাহু ব্ৰহ্মপুত্ৰ মহামিলনৰ তীৰ্থ, কত যুগ ধৰি আহিছে প্ৰকাশি সমন্বয়ৰ অৰ্থ। (Mahabahu Brahmaputra mahamilanor tirtha, Koto Zug Dhori Ahise Prokaxi Xomonoyor Artho)	O mighty Brahmaputra, pilgrimage of the great confluence; for ages you've revealed the meaning of harmony (B
<i>Xihu</i>	Gangetic river dolphin (local Assamese name)
<i>Guwa</i>	Areca Nut
<i>Hati</i>	Market
<i>Tekeli Pitha</i>	Traditional Assamese steamed rice cake co
<i>Laal Saah</i>	Black tea (strong, reddish Assamese tea)
<i>Singra</i>	Samosa
<i>Adda</i>	Informal casual gathering and long conversation
<i>Bihu</i>	Major traditional Assamese harvest festival
<i>Mayabini</i> (মায়াবিনী)	Popular song by Zubeen Garg

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Word or Phrase	Translation in English
<i>Zubeen Da</i>	Affectionate local reference to singer Zubeen Garg
<i>Bharalu</i>	River flowing through the heart of Guwahati
<i>Deepor Beel</i>	Famous freshwater wetland and Ramsar site in Guwahati
<i>Saah</i>	Tea
<i>Dighalipukhuri</i>	Historic rectangular pond and landmark in central Guwahati
<i>Uzan Bazar</i>	Historic riverfront market and ghat area along the Brahmaputra
<i>Panbazar</i>	Central commercial, bookshop, and cultural hub of Guwahati
<i>Maa Kamakhya</i>	The goddess worshipped at Kamakhya Temple
<i>Yoni shrine</i>	The sacred natural rock symbol representing the goddess at Kamakhya Temple
জীৱনৰ অৰ্থ হ'ল নতুন সপোন দেখা। (<i>Jibonor ortho hol notun sapon dekha</i>)	The meaning of life is to have more dreams
<i>Pragjyotishpura</i>	Ancient name of Guwahati (“City of Eastern Light”) mentioned in the Mahabharata
<i>Ambubachi Mela</i>	Annual three-day festival at Kamakhya Temple when the goddess is believed to menstruate

Everyday Life

Everyday Life

Mornings in Guwahati arrive carrying two very different energies at once. Near Dighalipukhuri pond, Syeda Tarrannum Shazadi, an English Literature student, slips out of her paying-guest room just after eight. She skips the electric rickshaw and walks the short stretch to Cotton University. The water catches the first light and gives off that cool, damp smell of pond and mud. One can witness people enjoying boating in the pond. “The water, the trees, and the quiet movement of people... create a calm atmosphere,” she told me. “That short walk almost feels like a transition between my personal space and the university.” The early morning streets already carry the warm steamed smell of ‘tekeli pitha’ and the deep earthy aroma of ‘laal saah’ brewing in small stalls where locals pause for that first sip and bite.

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Across town in Chandmari, Dr Sayanika Dutta has been awake since half past six. She packs her young daughter's lunch and daycare bag. She checks the time twice, then eases the car into the morning stream heading toward Panbazar. She remarked that she needs to be extra careful while driving as she also has her toddler with her, and morning hours are always very rushed as working professionals are travelling to the office, students are travelling to colleges, schools, etc. Two ordinary starts on the same day, both shaped by the same quiet hope that the roads will cooperate and the small rituals of beginning will hold.

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The day settles into its uneven but deeply familiar rhythm. By nine, Syeda Tarrannum Shazadi is already deep inside Cotton University, moving between lectures, discussions with classmates, departmental work and assignments. “Most of my day is spent inside Cotton University,” she said. “Campus feels almost like an extended living space because I spend so much time in and around there.” The hum of voices in the corridors, the distant thwack of a shuttlecock from the indoor stadium badminton courts, and students rushing from one class to another all blend into one steady background that makes the long hours feel like home. At roughly the same hour, Dr Sayanika Dutta reaches her department after the school drop-off, settling into a full day that ends with the evening pickup and the drive home by half past six.

For many, the commute itself becomes the longest part of the day. Disha Dutta leaves home very early because construction makes the trip stretch to nearly two hours each way. She returns by six and still finds the journey tiring. Adri Sarkar, a 22-year-old, has largely switched to bike taxis. “Because of the flyover work and traffic, public transport has become less reliable,” he explained. “It takes me more than 2 hours by public transport... Rapido is the only way for me to be able to reach college without sacrificing my sleep too much.” He now spends two to two-and-a-half hours commuting daily. Shahina Jannat once left more than an hour early for an important end-of-semester exam yet at twelve forty-five, she was still stuck in Maligaon traffic. “It was a very stressful day, and I still remember it vividly,” she recalled. “Experiences like that make traffic something I genuinely dread.”

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Evenings bring their own quiet closure. Pranabjit Bordoloi winds down by feeding his two dogs, watching television, spending time with his pets and going to bed around eleven. “In the evening, there is no special form of entertainment,” he shared. “I watch some television, use my phone, spend time with my pets and then go to bed.”

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Bhargab Bezbaruah starts and ends his day with walks around Uzan Bazar. “My morning usually starts around 8 a.m. I wake up and go for a walk around the Uzan Bazar area,” he said. In the evening, he returns to the recently renovated park there where the river breeze carries the faint scent of wet earth and distant incense. Mayur Gopendra Das often heads to the Brahmaputra Heritage Centre, which also has a Starbucks in its premises and sits peacefully as the light softens. “That’s where the city feels like home again,” he told me quietly.

Many evenings find residents turning to the songs of Zubeen Garg (fondly referred to as Zubeen Da by the people of Assam) for that familiar comfort. Mayur Gopendra Das often shares how Zubeen Da’s melodies have become the quiet soundtrack of everyday life here. They carry the same restless yet rooted spirit that runs through the city itself. As the light fades, lines from “Mayabini” drift on the breeze:

“মায়াবিনী ৰাতিৰ বুকুত
দেখা পালোঁ তোমাৰ ছবি
ধৰা দিলা গোপনে আহি
হিয়াৰ কোণত...”

Roughly, it translates to
“In the magical night’s heart,
I saw your image,
Silently, you touched a hidden corner of my heart.”

EVERYDAY LIFE

For Guwahati's citizens, those words capture the gentle pull of the river, the warmth of 'addas' and the way the city keeps drawing them back, no matter how fast it changes. Zubeen Da's songs hold a deep place in daily life because they remind people who they are. They turn ordinary evenings into something shared and lasting. Pranabjit Bordoloi, a senior citizen, remarked, "Wherever the people of Guwahati or the people of Assam are, they instantly feel at home when they listen to Zubeen Garg's songs." The songs of Zubeen Garg or Bhupen Hazarika are that cultural anchor that binds the people of Guwahati with the land and makes them feel the pride of their identity.

Comforts surface in small repeated places that still hold the city together. Syeda Tarrannum Shazadi cherishes the calm of Dighalipukhuri and the easy hours at her favourite café, "Bakehouse" near Lamb Road, where she can sit for hours with friends talking about life, studies or random thoughts. The warm, sweet smell of chocolate truffle pastry lingers in the air as laughter spills across the tables. Shahina Jannat unwinds at "Old Town Cafe", a small café in Panbazar. It is observed that the young generation has started finding solace and comfort spaces in the cafes mushrooming at a rapid pace in every nook and corner of Guwahati.

EVERYDAY LIFE

Yet, evenings also pulse with the city's famous adda culture or informal gatherings at tea stalls and lakeside benches where students, teachers, advocates and neighbours sit for hours talking about life, studies and the day's small frustrations while plates of steaming momo and crisp puchka make the rounds. Frequent ethnic fairs and melas spring up across the city, and Guwahatians never miss the chance to savour the smoky flavours of barbequed meat, ethnic delicacies and traditional juices.

Some find real relief when they push past the city's edges. A short ride brings you to Deepor Beel, Assam's only Ramsar-designated wetland since 2002. The vast freshwater lake can spread across more than four thousand hectares in the monsoon and supports over 219 bird species, including more than seventy migratory ones. There are avid birdwatchers in the city who consider Deepor Beel a real heaven. Early in the day, the waters come alive with egrets, herons and the kingfishers while the air feels noticeably cleaner, carrying the soft green scent of marsh grass and damp earth rather than the usual dust and exhaust. Further out in areas like Khamrenga in Chandrapur, narrow roads wind through pockets of forest and low hills where the constant city noise finally drops away. Boating in Khamrenga Beel is a raw, earthy experience that truly gives the essence of Guwahati, being the Gateway City to the Northeast of India. The boating there is not largely commercialised; it's just a few local families who will politely ask if you want a ride across the 'Beel' or lake in their small local boats. It's a very homely affair. As families spread picnic sheets on weekends, birdwatchers arrive before first light, and many simply sit on the bank letting the breeze off the water ease the accumulated weight of the week. Swapnil Dutta, who often seeks out these green corners, says heading to Deepor Beel or similar spots feels like hitting reset. "The noise of the city disappears, and you remember why this place still feels special," he told me.

These comforts coexist with relentless frictions. Mallika Sarmah and Shahina Jannat describe how returning home becomes exhausting because of traffic and sudden diversions. Regular users complain about buses that vanish or change routes without warning. Many interviewees highlighted how construction forces people to plan extra time or switch to costlier options. Adri Sarkar notes the dust and congestion that now make even short walks tiring. He pointed out that floods frequently damage roads. Jeet Pathak walks the regular highways near his home where vehicles race past with few speed breakers. Broken footpaths, open manholes and uneven surfaces turn every step risky. “Even footpaths can be unsafe because of broken surfaces, open manholes and uneven roads,” he said. “So walking in many parts of the city can be challenging.”

Bhargab Bezbaruah and others observe that while new green buses are improving the experience for some, “traffic congestion is also increasing” due to more vehicles and projects like the Chandmari flyover closure.

These patterns persist because Guwahati has expanded faster than its systems could keep up. With a population nearing 1.44 million and roughly 1,00,000 people depending on city buses every single day, the pressure shows everywhere. Construction sites chew up entire stretches for months at a time. The Chandmari flyover closure diverts heavy traffic onto narrow lanes that were never built for it.

EVERYDAY LIFE

Dust hangs thick in the air from endless digging, and two-wheelers now dominate the roads, weaving between potholes and ignoring signals at places like Ulubari. Average speeds on congested corridors crawl painfully low. Short rains turn streets into lakes because drains clog with waste, and the waterlogging has become so routine that people simply plan around it. Footpaths crumble underfoot with open manholes and broken slabs, turning a simple walk into an obstacle course. The city technically connects people, yet the daily experience leaves students missing lectures, mothers running late and older residents exhausted before the sun sets.

The voices show that while some improvements, such as new buses or flyovers, are appreciated, the overall effect for most people remains one of constant adjustment and fatigue.

What these ordinary days reveal about Guwahati is a city that still knows how to feel intimate morning walks beside water, familiar parks at sunset, campus lanes that feel like an extension of home, evening ‘addas’ and favourite food corners, yet is quietly learning to live with exhaustion as part of daily life. The voices show how small delays cascade into structural fatigue that affects everyone differently yet connects them all. If policymakers truly understood these rhythms, they would realise that the real challenge is not simply adding more concrete or wider roads. It is making the city’s daily movements reliable, predictable bus routes that do not disappear, pedestrian paths that remain safe after dark, construction that does not swallow entire neighbourhoods for months on end and traffic systems that remember the long-time residents who move through them every single day. Only then can the gentle transitions, shared addas and warmth that still define Guwahati remain its heartbeat instead of being slowly squeezed out by its own growth.

Places of Belonging

Places of Belonging

Building on the everyday activities of Guwahati, the short morning walks, crowded bus rides, campus hours, and evening pauses, certain spaces stand out as quiet anchors. They are where people return not because they must but because these places hold memories, conversations, and a deep sense of being at home in the city. Across interviews with students, teachers, working parents, and long-time residents, seven places repeatedly surface as emotionally important.

PLACES OF BELONGING

Dighalipukhuri is one of the most mentioned everyday anchors. Syeda Tarrannum Shazadi walks its edge almost every morning from her PG room in the same area. The water catches the early light and carries that cool, damp smell of pond and mud. Disha Dutta, a twenty-year-old, shares, “Oh! I love the Digholi Pukhuri area, I think it's still like the pure old Guwahati that it used to be”. Dighalipukhuri remained one of those areas in Guwahati that reminded the long-time residents about the peace and tranquillity amidst the city chaos that Guwahati offered around 10-15 years ago. Dighalipukhuri is the area in Guwahati where the mystical nature of the greenish-blue pond, the hundreds of years old trees, countless species of birds and small animals interact with the ever-growing city bustle and development that can be seen in huge establishments, fancy cafes all around, flyovers, etc.

Dighalipukhuri itself carries centuries of stories. Legend has it that King Bhagadatta of ancient Pragjyotishpur dug the long rectangular pond for his daughter Bhanumati's swayamvara, carving a canal that once drew water straight from the Brahmaputra. By the time of the Ahom kings, it had become a vital naval dockyard where boats were built, repaired, and launched for battles against the Mughals. Even after the British closed its river connection and filled part of the land for the old Circuit House and later the Gauhati High Court, the pond stayed at the quiet centre of old Guwahati. Generations have walked its edges ever since, drawn by the same calm water that once floated warships and now catches the first light for students hurrying to class or neighbours pausing on their morning rounds.

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Its emotional meaning lies in the simple daily grounding it provides. Yet it has faced serious change. Citizens protested strongly when large numbers of trees were cut at night during flyover construction. Sabique Hasan, an environmental activist, recalled, “I remember trees being cut at night when the lights were switched off.” Development pressure and infrastructure projects have reduced its open feel, while recent renovations have brought more crowds. Who feels welcome? Students, families, and morning walkers who value calm starts. Who doesn’t? Those who remember its quieter past and now find it busier. Development here should be careful because this place carries both everyday rituals and the collective memory of citizens who stood up to protect its trees.

Uzanbazar Ghat along the Brahmaputra riverfront remains the city’s most deeply felt public space. The wide muddy sweep rolls past, carrying silt from far upstream, and the river breeze brings the faint scent of wet earth and distant incense. Mrinmoyee Sarmah Bordoloi says simply, “Uzan bazar, the view of the Brahmaputra, if that disappears, nothing matters anymore.” Dr Sayanika Dutta first came here as a student walking from the Cotton University hostel. “My friends and I would often walk there... Even today, that place holds many memories for me,” she shared. Families stroll in the evenings, students sit alone watching the river, and older residents find peace on the benches. The ghat has been central since well before the city expanded rapidly, tied to the Brahmaputra that has always defined Guwahati’s identity. Its cultural and historical significance is immense as a living

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riverfront. Development pressure and restricted access are slowly shrinking the open stretches. Who feels welcome? Almost everyone who is seeking reflection or connection with the river. Development here should be careful because this place carries memories across generations and the cultural soul of the city itself.

Bhupen Hazarika captured something of that pull in his lines “মহাবাহু ব্রহ্মপুত্র মহামিলনৰ তীৰ্থ, কত যুগ ধৰি আহিছে প্ৰকাশি সমন্বয়ৰ অৰ্থ।” It translates to “O mighty Brahmaputra, pilgrimage of the great confluence, for ages you’ve revealed the meaning of harmony.” Standing here, those words feel less like poetry and more like the quiet conversation the city has always had with its river.

Rabindra Bhawan stands as a cultural landmark that many still mourn in its current state. The old auditorium once hustled with the murmur of crowds settling into seats, the rustle of programmes, and the sudden hush before a play began. Mallika Sarmah described it as part of her inner life, “Rabindra Bhawan was not just a building to me, it was a part of my inner life. The programmes, the cultural events...” Arghya Saha grew up watching plays there. “A large part of my childhood memories is connected to Rabindra Bhawan.” The hall has hosted theatre, films, and public events since the mid-20th century, making it a historic centre for arts and

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intellectual discussion in Guwahati. Its emotional meaning lies in the shared cultural experiences it once offered. Neglect and prolonged closure for renovation, along with nearby flyover construction, have left it diminished. The older residents and artists who remember its vibrant past feel welcomed here. But the younger people who never got to experience the cultural magic of Rabindra Bhawan do not feel the same connection. Development here should be careful because this place carries the city's artistic heritage and childhood memories of generations.

Kamakhya Temple on Nilachal Hill is more than a religious site. It is a living symbol of faith and continuity for countless residents. Guwahatians, irrespective of religion believe in the power of Maa Kamakhya and feel that the goddess will always protect Guwahati from all kinds of dangers. The climb up the stone steps leaves you breathing hard, the air thick with the sharp scent of incense, marigolds, and the strong divine aura of a holy power inside. Rahul Rohan Paul, an aspiring journalist, visits whenever he returns to the city and finds the same spiritual calm he felt growing up. Pranabjit Bordoloi, who manages his daily routines around the city, speaks of the temple as a place of deep personal connection and peace. Devotees climb the hill for darshan, families offer prayers during festivals, and people from all walks of life come seeking blessings before an exam, a job interview, or a journey.

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The temple's ancient history as one of the most revered Shakti Peethas links Guwahati to centuries of spiritual tradition. Once a year, during Ambubachi Mela the temple draws lakhs of devotees and sadhus from across the country as the goddess is believed to go through her annual cycle. For three days, the doors remain closed while the entire hill comes alive with chants, colours, and quiet anticipation. Its cultural and historical significance is profound, drawing pilgrims and locals alike. Changing lifestyles have brought more visitors, but the temple itself remains a source of strength and belonging. Devotees, families, aspirants and anyone seeking spiritual solace feel welcomed here. "Development here should be careful because this place carries a deep spiritual connection and positive faith that continues to unite people across the city," Pranabjit Bordoloi expressed. From the hilltop, the city and the Brahmaputra spread out below, a reminder that whatever rushes below still feels anchored here.

Cafes and tea stalls like Moon Da's near Cotton University form the city's informal social backbone. The small plastic stools scrape against concrete, the steam from fresh 'Saah', and the low hum of voices never quite dies. "Moon Da's and the small tea stalls near Cotton University are like our second home. After classes, we just sit there for hours, talking about everything from exams to life plans. No one is in a hurry!" says Arunava Borah. Similar are the thoughts of countless students like Himparna Borah, who expressed, "Places like Loyans in Uzan Bazar or Kadak Chai are where real adda happens. You don't need any plan. Someone is always there, and the conversation just flows for hours." These small eateries, whether Moon Da's or others, have existed for years as natural gathering places. Their emotional meaning is simple as they embody a sense of warmth, friendship, and unhurried talk about studies, life, and the day's events. Changing lifestyles and road-widening projects are gradually reducing space for these lingering corners.

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Panbazar is often described as the living heart of Guwahati. The narrow lanes hum with the clatter of rickshaws, the calls of bookshop owners, and the sweet sticky smell of sweets and the fresh smell of warm bread from the bakeries like Shaikh Brothers, Diamond Bakery and others. Hrishikesh Medhi, a Psychology Scholar, calls it “the heart of the city” and says, “If Panbazar disappears, the city will feel the absence.” That absence would matter because this is where history, commerce, learning, and daily life have always tangled together, the old character of narrow book-lined streets, small eateries, and the steady rhythm of students, teachers, lawyers, and shopkeepers who know each other by name after years of the same routines. Arhana Bhuyan and many students treat the bookshops, small eateries, and streets around Cotton University as daily extensions of campus life. The area has been the commercial and educational core since the city’s early growth, with historic markets and institutions. Development pressure from new constructions has changed its old character. Mohixit Goswami expressed the same attachment in stronger terms. “Panbazar is an area that I feel like is quintessentially Guwahati,” he told me. “I think the city breeds truly in this area the most, and the personality that any city has. I think that personality truly reflects in the Guwahati area with Panbazar and Uzanbazar with all the establishments that surround it, especially with the High Court, bookshops, Shaikh Brothers and whatnot.” He shows why Panbazar

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feels like the soul of Guwahati to so many residents: it is the place where history, commerce, learning, and daily life have blended for generations, giving the city its distinct identity. This perspective adds depth because it comes from a young voice who has known no other Guwahati, making the attachment feel both personal and representative of an entire generation.

Gandhi Mandap on the small hilltop offers a different kind of belonging. The path winds up through thick trees on the steep hill, and the air cools as you climb, the soft crunch of dry leaves underfoot, the distant call of birds replacing the city's constant hum. Sabique Hasan Ahmed visits the Gandhi Mandap hill whenever he feels low. "It is surreal to me... it is like my go-to place whenever I feel low or whenever I feel bored," he said. "It has a lot of trees... I would just sit under a tree." Other residents, like those interviewed, mention it for quiet walks and nature. The mandap has served as a peaceful green spot for generations. Its emotional meaning comes from providing solitude and connection with greenery amid urban life. Changing lifestyles and surrounding development have made access slightly harder, yet it remains a favourite. In a city undergoing rapid urban expansion, such spaces appear to play an increasingly important restorative role. The mandap continues to hold strong appeal as one of the few remaining places where residents can find personal emotional refuge and reconnection with greenery.

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Across these seven places runs one clear thread: they welcome students, working mothers, retirees, teachers, and young professionals alike, offering different kinds of belonging: calm, culture, faith, conversation, and history. Yet each feels increasingly fragile under development pressure, neglect of older sites, and shifting urban lifestyles. The interviews show that when citizens protested tree-cutting at Dighalipukhuri, or when people spoke with genuine emotion about Rabindra Bhawan or the riverfront, they were protecting something deeper than land or buildings. These spaces carry the stories, rituals, and connections that turn a growing city into a place people truly call home. If Guwahati expands without safeguarding them, it risks losing the very things that make its residents feel they belong.

Voices of Concern

Voices of Concern

Listening to people across Guwahati, one feeling cuts through every conversation. The city is changing fast, but the change lands hardest on daily life. It is not just an inconvenience. It is a slow, grinding sense that the places they love are being taken apart in the name of development, and few seem to hear how it actually feels on the ground.

Swapnil Dutta said with grief, “Drainage system or the flood issues of Assam... during the monsoon season, whenever rain occurs, there’s always flash floods and waterlogging.” This is one of the most significant problems faced by the citizens of Guwahati. On the tragic night of 19 April 2026, a resident of Guwahati, Payel Nath, slipped and fell into an open roadside drain in Maligaon amid heavy rain and severe waterlogging. Her body was recovered hours later. All educational institutions stayed closed the next day. The tragedy was not an isolated accident. It was the latest reminder of drains that stay uncovered and a drainage system that cannot keep pace with the rain.

Disha Dutta described the new normal of dust. “You can literally see the dust particles in the air.” She added something that stayed with me: the constant construction leaves her wondering about her own health. “In no time we’ll get respiratory diseases, I feel.” Official readings back her up. In February 2026, the city’s AQI spiked to 294, firmly in the poor category, driven largely by construction dust and dry spells. Even now in late April, it hovers in the moderate-to-poor range, with PM2.5 often three to seven times above safe limits. What used to be occasional haze has become the air people breathe every morning.

Dudulmoni Sarmah has watched decades of change and spoken with the weight of someone seeing something beautiful slip away. “In the name of development, all the trees have been cut... we have ruined this beautiful city.” He described how the green mountains that used to refresh travellers arriving by train are now covered in buildings. What makes his words heavy is that he is not against growth. He knows cities must change. But he sees the growth as unplanned and careless. Original residents feel pushed aside, and with them, the deep sense of ownership. “This feeling of ‘Guwahati is mine’... it is all lost.” The indifference, he said, comes from both the public and the government. “The civic sense that must stay inherent in one, neither resides with the public nor with the government.” That double failure has left the city slowly suffocating. An instance supporting his statements is that only hours after the grand inauguration of the new Kumar Bhaskar Varma Setu linking Guwahati and North Guwahati, the bridge was already strewn with plastic waste, empty bottles, and garbage left by visitors and vendors. The viral images made the point sharper than any speech could.

Dr Rashmi Sarmah, a freelance journalist and educationist, pointed to a harder truth, i.e., citizens themselves sometimes feed the problem. She spoke of cars left idling with AC running, plastic burned with garden waste, and sanitation workers setting tyres alight at night. These are not distant environmental issues. They are daily choices that add to the very pollution everyone complains about.

The same tension runs through other voices. Mohixit Goswami called out “Guwahati’s race to be the city of flyovers” while enormous drains run thick with sewage. Over the past decade, Guwahati has added around ten to eleven major flyovers, with several more under construction at the same time. The city recently crossed the mark of thirty flyovers, including the longest in the Northeast. Construction sites chew up roads and neighbourhoods simultaneously, yet traffic queues have not eased in the way people hoped.

Kankan Bordoloi described how even parks meant for children now have broken equipment and so much pollution that parents keep their kids away. Avilasha Bhowmik talked about green buses that stop anywhere, sparking morning fights and delays that leave students late and scolded. Hrishikesh Medhi noted that traffic has become so ordinary that nobody blinks when students miss 9 a.m. classes.

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Abhijnan Barhoi brought another angle. He described roads dug up again and again for water pipelines that leak soon after and remarked, “Roads are dug up, rebuilt and then dug again when pipelines leak. This constant cycle wastes public funds and causes inconvenience for residents.” In Kharghuli, the pattern repeated painfully when a JICA water supply mainline pipe burst in January 2025, flooding the neighbourhood with knee-deep water, wasting thousands of litres and also severely injuring local people. Similar bursts have happened before, exposing delays and quality gaps in the very projects meant to fix the city’s water problems.

These are not the voices of people who hate change. Many praised smoother stretches of road or new cafés in Panbazar and Lal Ganesh. Some welcomed renovated parks near the DC bungalow. The grief is not about rejecting progress. It is about the way progress arrives to the city rather than for the people living in it. They still love the Brahmaputra, the old lanes of Uzan Bazar and Panbazar, the warmth that surfaces in unplanned addas. But they feel those things disappearing under their feet.

Even the Gangetic river dolphins that once broke the surface near Uzan Bazar have become a symbol of what is slipping away. Just a few years ago, spotting an Xihu from the various ghats in Guwahati was a common, almost everyday sight. Over the years, the numbers have fallen sharply. Pollution, sand mining, and habitat destruction have all taken their toll. Spotting a dolphin now feels like a rare gift rather than something you expect. Young people have started raising their voices; the 1st ever ‘River Dolphin Festival’ was organised in Cotton University in January 2026 by the youth determined to keep the Xihu from vanishing completely.

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What the interviews show is a painful gap. On paper, Guwahati is modernising with flyovers, wider roads, more commercial space and many more developments. On the ground, residents breathe dust, wade through floods, lose their trees, and watch free public places become expensive or vanish. The concerns are personal, including health strained by pollution, fear of walking home at night, hours lost in traffic that could have been spent with family or studies, and the slow ache of watching the city they belong to be redesigned without their say.

This is why the voices feel heavy. It is not anger for its own sake. It is people who still care deeply about Guwahati saying, in their own words, that the current model of development is breaking the very things that make the city worth living in. They see the new cafés and some better roads. They also see the disappearing green cover, the floods that have become routine, the waste that clogs everything, and the quiet sense that no one in power is truly listening.

Dreams for Tomorrow

Dreams for Tomorrow

“জীৱনৰ অৰ্থ হ’ল নতুন সপোন দেখা।”

The meaning of life is to have more dreams. That simple Assamese truth still resonates in the early morning tea stalls along the Brahmaputra and during Bihu celebrations when families gather under the open sky. It reminds every Guwahati resident that tomorrow is not about forgetting the river that has shaped their lives or the green hills that once welcomed them. It is about dreaming bigger while holding those roots close. People here are not chasing some distant utopia. They want a Guwahati that grows without erasing the river, the green pockets, the places where conversations flow without a bill, and the quiet feeling that this city still belongs to the ones who live in it.

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Dudulmoni Sarmah has seen decades roll by. He does not reject development. He wants planned and sustainable development that maintains ecological balance, protection and expansion of open spaces, and improved public transportation. He believes it is possible because Guwahati was once genuinely beautiful and geographically blessed, with rivers like the Bharalu flowing right through the middle of the city. “We could have protected and preserved the beautiful city of Guwahati,” he said, if planning had started earlier. For him, the need is simply to maintain what nature has already given rather than destroy it. The same man who watched trees fall and hills disappear still holds onto the idea that growth and nature can walk together if we stop treating the river and the remaining green cover as obstacles.

His call for planned, sustainable growth is practical but demands a sharp shift in how the Guwahati Metropolitan Development Authority and the Municipal Corporation operate. The city already has pieces in place with the recent addition of more electric buses and several new flyovers, showing that infrastructure money exists. What is missing is coordination across departments so that every new road or building project automatically includes wetland protection and open-space offsets. With a population increasing day by day and daily pressure on the Bharalu and Brahmaputra, the solution is not cheap. Yet it is achievable if citizen groups are given real seats at the planning table before projects break ground, turning protests into preventive policy.

Swapnil Dutta added a quieter but equally important layer. “The only place which is still quite green is the university campus,” he said, and he sees Panbazar as holding the core emotion of Guwahati. Yet he also spoke about a growing emotional detachment from places that once felt like home. He feels the daily requirements of the people are already met. What he wants is careful preservation of the existing green lungs and heritage zones so that people do not slowly lose their emotional connection to the city.

Preserving these pockets is one of the most immediately doable dreams. Recent tree-felling protests at Dighalipukhuri proved that residents will mobilise fast when they see green disappearing overnight. A practical next step would be a city-wide heritage and green inventory that flags these sites as non-negotiable, backed by simple municipal orders rather than lengthy court battles. The cost is low. The payoff in resident belonging is high.

Kankan Bordoloi shared the same practical ambition. He wants “an integrated master plan that brings together transport, drainage, heritage preservation, and reduced dependence on private vehicles.” He is realistic about the timeline. “10–15 years down the line there can be tremendous development, but only if action starts now with vision and execution.” He believes it is possible because Guwahati already sits at a strategic location and has received major investments.

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An integrated master plan sounds ambitious, yet the building blocks already exist in scattered form. The real test is enforcement, as past master plans have gathered dust because they lacked binding timelines and citizen oversight. If the state government ties future funding to measurable yearly progress, and if residents are consulted before each phase rather than after construction begins, the ten-to-fifteen-year horizon becomes realistic rather than wishful.

Arghya Saha dreams of something more specific and deeply felt. “I would be really proud if Guwahati becomes the Cleanest City on the Banks of the Brahmaputra,” he said, “where the river is treated as sacred instead of a backyard for waste.” He wants the community spirit of Bihu to survive even as the city gets bigger. He believes it is possible because that warmth and river connection still exist in people’s hearts.

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Turning the Brahmaputra and Bharalu into clean, proud assets is practical at the neighbourhood level first. Waste segregation at source, already piloted in some wards, needs scaling with door-to-door collection and fines that actually stick. The emotional pull of Bihu gatherings on the riverbank gives authorities a ready-made cultural lever to imagine community-led river clean-ups tied to festival dates. The bigger challenge is industrial and municipal sewage, which requires serious investment in treatment plants.

Bhargab Bezbaruah, speaking as a young citizen, wants ambitious but people-centred infrastructure. “I want a Science City like Kolkata’s, a world-class stadium, and a well-maintained ropeway that actually works as a tourist attraction,” he said. He is not against the new flyovers; he thinks they can help if traffic rules are enforced properly. He believes it is possible because citizens are already showing they care. He himself joined protests to save trees in Dighalipukhuri.

Big-ticket projects like a Science City or functional ropeway are feasible only if they ride on existing momentum. A ropeway, for instance, fails when upkeep is ignored. Enforcing traffic rules on the new flyovers is simpler and cheaper with cameras, graduated fines, and school-level awareness campaigns, which could cut chaos without new concrete.

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Arunava Borah wants infrastructure and job opportunities so that people from Assam do not have to leave the state, but balanced with nature. “Development should not mean replacing everything with concrete,” she said. Himparna Das hopes for a city where children can walk safely, breathe cleaner air, and still see birds, trees, and open skies. Both believe it is possible because Guwahati still has the natural beauty and the warmth that make people want to stay.

Creating local jobs while protecting nature is perhaps the most grounded dream of all. Guwahati’s location makes it a natural hub for eco-tourism, river-based logistics, and small-scale green industries. The challenge lies in skill training that matches actual market gaps rather than generic schemes. Safe pedestrian paths and clean air for kids require modest but consistent spending on footpaths, speed breakers, and dust-control measures around construction sites. Because the natural beauty is still here, small wins compound fast: one restored ghat, one traffic-calmed school route, one new pocket park can convince young families to stay.

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Dr Sayanika Dutta added the quiet but powerful desire for safety and inclusivity. She wants Guwahati to remain a safe city for her daughter, with gender equality and sensitivity toward different communities. “I hope the city retains its green cover,” she said. “Trees and greenery are extremely important for maintaining ecological balance and controlling pollution. I also hope Guwahati remains a safe city.” She believes it is possible because, compared to many other Indian cities, Guwahati still feels relatively secure even late at night.

Retaining green cover while keeping the city safe for women and children is entirely practical and mutually reinforcing. Trees reduce urban heat and pollution; well-lit, tree-lined footpaths improve both air quality and perceived safety. The city already feels safer than many metros after dark, so the task is to protect that advantage through simple measures like better street lighting, regular police patrolling in residential pockets, and community watch groups linked to local apps. Green cover targets can be met by mandating a certain percentage of tree canopy in every new project. The cost is manageable, and the health and social returns are immediate.

Across all these voices, one hears the same recurring dreams. A city that grows thoughtfully instead of chaotically, that protects its remaining green cover and riverfront instead of concretising them, that revives free, safe public spaces where people of all ages can gather without spending money, that improves waste management and drainage so floods and filth stop being accepted as normal, that creates real jobs so the city’s own youth do not have to leave, and that gives citizens an actual voice in how their city is shaped. People are not against modern infrastructure. Many appreciate the new roads and cafés. But they want development that respects the city’s soul rather than replacing it.

The biggest shift needed is in mindset and systems. Development must stop being treated as a series of disconnected projects and become a single, integrated master plan that puts ecology, heritage, and livability first. Behaviour has to change too. Both citizens and the government need to move from “not my problem” apathy to shared responsibility. Small daily habits like waste segregation, not burning plastic, and turning off car engines matter just as much as big policy decisions.

Some of these changes are practical and feasible in the next few years. Better waste collection and segregation, regular cleaning of existing parks and river ghats, stricter enforcement of traffic rules on new flyovers, and creating a few genuine free public adda spaces, perhaps by reviving the old coffee-house culture, can build trust quickly. These are doable with better municipal coordination and citizen pressure.

Other hopes require deeper structural reform. A proper drainage master plan, legal protection of remaining wetlands and hills, a clear policy on tree felling linked to every construction project, and real citizen assemblies where people can question development proposals before they are approved. Responsibility lies with the

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Guwahati Municipal Corporation, the Guwahati Metropolitan Development Authority, and the state government, but citizens must hold them accountable.

The interviews show that citizens are already playing their part. People are protesting tree felling, organising cleanup drives, teaching underprivileged children, and speaking up. The hope is that these individual efforts grow into sustained citizen vigilance and participation, so development is no longer something done to the city but something done with its people.

The biggest obstacles are not money or technology. They are the lack of coordinated planning, the habit of treating citizen voices as something to be managed rather than listened to, and the quiet acceptance that this is how it is. The love for Guwahati is still very much alive, for its river, its remaining green pockets, its warmth, and its potential. The question is whether we can turn that love into consistent pressure and practical action before the things people cherish most slip away for good. The interviews show that the dreams are clear and realistic. What we need now is the collective will to make them real.

Policy Insights

Policy Insights

Going through multiple interviews of the diverse set of citizens of Guwahati, the same patterns keep coming up in different voices and from different parts of life. People are not against the idea of a bigger, more modern Guwahati. The interviews turn personal stories into very clear signals about where the system is falling short and what practical changes could actually make daily life better. Here are some structural issues that surface again and again, each one backed by what citizens repeatedly said.

The first is mobility and daily accessibility. Almost everyone described how flyover and overbridge construction has narrowed roads, created endless dust, and turned simple bus rides or walks into exhausting ordeals. Swapnil Dutta said the university campus is now “the only place which is still quite green” because the rest of the city feels chaotic. Arhana Bhuyan put it bluntly, “If you cannot breathe well, you cannot really think well either.” The implementation gap is obvious, i.e., multiple agencies start projects at the same time without proper traffic management or phased planning. In the short term, the GMC and traffic police could immediately put marshals and temporary diversions at every active construction site and enforce peak-hour rules strictly. In the medium term, the GMDA needs to coordinate all ongoing projects through a single dashboard so citizens know what is happening when. Long-term, the city needs a comprehensive public transport master plan under the Smart City Mission and AMRUT 2.0 that actually reduces private vehicle use instead of just adding more lanes. The stakeholders who must act are the Public Works Department, GMDA, GMC, and local bus operators, working with resident groups so solutions are grounded in real commuting patterns.

The second issue is flooding and drainage failure. From seniors like Dudulmoni Sarmah to students like Arghya Saha, people said the same thing that even short rains leave streets waterlogged, and this has become so normal that no one is shocked anymore. Dudulmoni called it a “man-made problem created in the name of development.” The gap here is that old drainage maps are outdated, wetlands are still being filled, and legacy waste keeps blocking channels. Short-term, the GMC could run pre-monsoon desilting drives every year and clear choked drains in high-risk areas like Gandhibasti, Nabin-nagar and Anilnagar. The GMDA should update the drainage master plan and link it to the ongoing Smart City projects so new roads do not make flooding worse. Long-term, the state needs a wetland protection law and a policy that stops construction on natural water channels. Responsibility sits with the GMDA, the Irrigation Department, and the Pollution Control Board, but citizens have to stop throwing waste into drains if any of this is to work.

The third structural problem is the rapid loss of green cover and trees. Tree-felling for construction came up in almost every interview. Dudulmoni said, “In the name of development, all the trees have been cut... we have ruined this beautiful city.” Himparna Das spoke about the “thousands of mature trees being felled,” and Abhijan Barhoi described how repeated road digging for Jal Jeevan Mission pipelines wastes money and destroys whatever greenery is left. The gap is that there is no binding “no net loss” rule attached to every project, and compensatory planting is often delayed or poorly monitored. For the Short-term, the Forest Department could insist on immediate compensatory plantation on site or in the same ward before any tree is cut. Long-term, Guwahati must have a green infrastructure plan that treats existing trees and wetlands as non-negotiable assets in every development proposal. The Forest Department, GMDA, and local NGOs should lead, with active involvement from youth who already protest tree cutting.

The fourth issue is waste management and everyday cleanliness. Litter on footpaths, sewage-filled drains, and the “not my problem until it reaches my house” attitude were mentioned repeatedly. Dr Rashmi Sarmah gave concrete examples of citizens burning plastic and leaving car ACs running. The implementation gap is clear: waste segregation is promoted, but collection systems do not support it, and corporations are not held accountable for the packaging they create. Short-term, the GMC could run focused ward-level campaigns and increase daily sweeping in busy areas like Panbazar. Long-term, the city should move to a full circular waste system linked to the Swachh Bharat Mission. Stakeholders include the GMC, waste contractors, resident welfare associations, and schools, because behaviour change has to start at the neighbourhood level.

The fifth recurring gap is the maintenance and accessibility of public spaces and adda places. Kankan Bordoloi described parks with broken equipment that are unsafe for children, while young people like Avilasha and Arhana said cafés have become the only affordable hangouts because free spaces have disappeared or become commercial. The gap is that maintenance budgets are low, and citizen input is rarely sought. Long-term, the city needs a public-space policy that mandates free, inclusive gathering spots in every ward. The GMC, district administration, and cultural organisations should lead, with regular input from youth and senior citizen forums.

The sixth issue is the lack of genuine citizen participation and communication with authorities. Dudulmoni lamented the silence of citizens and the indifference of the government. Abhijnan and Sabique both spoke about the need for citizen assemblies before projects are approved. The gap is that public hearings are often formalities, and grievances disappear into files. In the short term, the GMDA could hold ward-level public meetings before any major project starts. Medium-term, it could create a live-streamed digital grievance portal with time-bound responses. Long-term, Guwahati needs a formal citizen participation framework similar to Gram Sabhas for urban areas. The state Urban Development Department, GMDA, and elected councillors are the key players, but student unions and neighbourhood groups must be brought in as equal partners.

The seventh and perhaps most foundational issue is the protection of cultural and social infrastructure alongside environmental health. From the Brahmaputra riverfront to Rabindra Bhawan, from Digholi Pukhuri to old bazaars, people repeatedly said they are losing the places that give the city its soul. Arghya Saha wanted Guwahati to become the “Cleanest City on the Banks of the Brahmaputra.” Bhargab Bezbaruah hoped for a Science City and world-class stadium that still respects the city’s identity. The gap is that heritage and ecology are treated as separate from development rather than part of it. Another pressing matter is the conservation of the Gangetic River Dolphin, Guwahati’s own city animal. Rising pollution, sand mining, and habitat destruction have made sightings rarer.

POLICY INSIGHTS

The gap is glaring. Protection laws exist on paper, but day-to-day monitoring and enforcement along the city's stretches of the river remain weak, especially as riverfront projects push forward.

In the short term, the district administration could protect and maintain heritage sites like Rabindra Bhawan and the river ghats. Medium-term, every major project should require a heritage and ecology impact assessment. Long-term, Guwahati needs an integrated urban development policy that treats culture, ecology, and livability as equal pillars. The stakeholders are the state Tourism and Cultural Departments, the GMDA, and citizen heritage groups.

Taken together, these seven issues show that Guwahati's problems are not random. They are the direct result of fragmented planning, weak enforcement, and a habit of treating citizens as beneficiaries rather than partners. The interviews also show something hopeful: people still love this city deeply and are willing to participate if given a real chance. The practical path forward is clear- better coordination between agencies, stricter enforcement of existing rules, modest budget shifts toward maintenance and green infrastructure, and regular platforms where citizens can speak before decisions are made. None of this requires impossible sums of money. It requires political will to listen, coordinate, and act on what people have been saying for years. The dreams citizens expressed are realistic and achievable.

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ANNEXURE

A few conversations truly shifted how I saw my own city. The conversations felt deep, and it really moved me and made me rethink those words multiple times after.

Dudulmoni Sarmah, a senior citizen and retired bank employee who now serves as secretary of Anwasha, a centre that promotes books and social initiatives, first came to Guwahati in the 1970s–80s to study. Back then, the city felt simple and sober. “More Assamese-type houses instead of buildings,” he recalled, with no flyovers and people moving from cycles to bikes. He pointed out the flyover at GNB Road where “houses and walls stand with barely any inches of gap,” and electrical wires run through those tight spaces, raising serious public safety concerns.

Dr Sayanika Dutta, Head of the Department of Mass Communication at Cotton University and a working mother, shared some of the small personal joys that often go unnoticed. “One small but enjoyable activity for me is having rasgullas from Ashok Sweets in Lachit Nagar.” She also spoke warmly about the everyday compassion people show towards stray animals: “I often notice people feeding stray dogs... buying biscuits just to feed them. This sense of compassion toward animals is something I find very heartwarming and is a sight I do not often see in larger metropolitan cities.” Yet she also pointed to the darker side of things; reports of stray dogs being kidnapped at night, some captured on CCTV and called for more NGOs, proper funding, volunteers, and community-based initiatives where

ANNEXURE

neighbourhoods take collective responsibility for animal welfare. The closure of the Chandmari flyover has made her daily drive especially stressful, as heavy traffic has been diverted onto the narrow lane where her daughter's daycare is located.

Also, she mentioned avoiding Jalukbari whenever possible, as “It has changed a lot and the roads and layouts feel confusing unless you are very familiar with the area.”

Swapnil Dutta, a young mass communication student with a keen interest in environmental issues, recalled how certain places have quietly lost their earlier magic. Zoo Road was once deeply nostalgic for him; he commented on it as “the first place I actually quite often visited as someone who transitioned into adulthood or even the last stage of teenage life”, but now it has changed significantly, and he rarely visits. He has made a firm personal commitment to stay in Assam and said, “I'll definitely be here regardless of whatever the issue comes up... I have personally decided to stay in Assam as a fellow indigenous person.” He also pointed out a very practical but often overlooked need, “We definitely need proper public restrooms, washrooms, also which are gender-friendly.”

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Ankita Sarmah Bordoloi

Ankita is from Guwahati, Assam and is a Master's student in Mass Communication and Journalism at Cotton University. With a passion for biodiversity conservation, event management, and stakeholder coordination, Ankita is a trilingual communicator skilled in Assamese, Hindi, and English. She is eager to leverage her academic expertise and hands-on experience to contribute meaningfully to media and communications while building professional excellence and fostering collaborative growth.

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Message from the Founders

Ten years ago, we set off on a journey across India's small towns. Over five months and fifty cities, we came through stories, crafts, silences, and dreams. We rediscovered that our smaller cities were not merely settlements; they were living archives of collective memory and identity—fossils of space and time inhabited by breath and imagination.

In Ratnagiri we were directed by many city experts to meet an auto mechanic. He was the go-to person for everyone in the city, including the city government, for engineering issues such as the city's water supply. He had seen the city evolve and remembered its various extensions, its water supply networks, and the various issues the city had faced in the last few decades. In Thanjavur, we sat with a veena-maker working 20-hour days in a modest shed, carving centuries of musical tradition into a single piece of jackfruit wood. We listened to bakers, poets, priests, and students. They told us not only what their cities were, but what they could become.

What struck us most was this: citizens carry the city's soul. The insights they hold—about its past, its present, and its future—are powerful, yet rarely represented in how cities are imagined or governed. This realization gave genesis to the Nāgrika Fellowship. It has been our attempt to honour the power of local voices—to create space for young people to observe, listen, document, and co-create city narratives from within. Each City Vision Document is not just a reflection of one fellow's journey; it's a collaborative act of remembering and imagining.

We hope this document stirs dialogue, ownership, and pride. And just like cities that shape their people, we hope this fellowship shapes a new kind of citizen—curious, rooted, and ready to lead.

We exist to ensure small-city voices, often unheard, have the knowledge and tools to influence the development and policies of their communities.

We focus on citizen-driven research. By engaging directly with small city communities, we present their authentic realities, untouched by outside narratives. This hands-on approach keeps small city voices at the heart of everything we do.

Citizen-Centred

It's always about the people. Small-city citizens are at the heart of everything we do.

Curious and Objective

Our approach stems from curiosity—focusing on the truth, making sure every voice in small cities is heard clearly and fairly.

Credible and Rooted

We are committed to producing knowledge and insight from the small cities that is dependable and high-quality.

Resourceful

We make the most of what we have, using our resources wisely to create valuable knowledge.

Small Cities, Big Love

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